

Development and Standardization of Polyherbal Suspension

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Abstract

The World Health Organization is encouraging the use of herbal formulations made from traditional medicinal plants in different nations. The present study's principal objective was to produce and characterize a polyherbal suspension using ethanolic extracts of selected parts of medicinal plants. Polyherbal Formulation-A, Polyherbal Formulation-B, and Polyherbal Formulation-C are three potential suspensions with ethanolic extracts of selected parts of medicinal plants and varying sodium carboxy methyl cellulose concentrations 1 %, 1.5 %, 2 % respectively formulated and evaluated for certain standard parameters like organoleptic characters, pH, viscosity, sedimentation volume, redispersibility, density, specific gravity, zeta potential and accelerated stability studies for 3 months. Evaluation parameters of Polyherbal Formulation-C have revealed good results that were within the specification, which exhibited a pleasant texture and appearance and other physiochemical properties like pH, viscosity, flow rate and sedimentation were all unchanged. It was discovered that every quality control parameter in the suspension formulation was comprehensive and appropriate. As a result, it is determined that a prepared polyherbal suspension includes ethanolic extracts of *Ricinus communis* L., *Moringa oleifera* Lam, *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss, *Tinospora cordifolia* (Thumb.) Miers, *Cymbopogon citrates* (DC.) Stapf may be stable, secure and effective for usage.

Keywords: Polyherbal formulation, Suspension, Stability testing, physiochemical, Standardization.

1.Introduction

Due to the growing public concern about the toxicity and adverse effects of allopathic medications, natural goods are going to become a vital part of the public health care system. The area of herbal medicine has grown exponentially in the last few decades as a result of growing interest around the world in natural, non-synthetic drugs derived from plants or herbs because of their improved tolerance and reduced risk of adverse drug reactions [1].

These medications are safe and especially useful for treating chronic conditions that need long-term care. To get the most advantage from their combined ability to minimize one another's side effects, Combinations are more commonly used for administering plant medicines than single form. With the aforementioned details in mind, an indigenous polyherbal remedy was developed [2].

Natural products like polyherbal formulations are more affordable, environmentally friendly, and easily accessible than pharmaceuticals. Their improved accessibility and affordability are driving up demand for them worldwide, especially in developing nations and rural areas where expensive current therapies are unavailable. Together with scientific advancements, polyherbal formulations have advanced due to the research of various phytoconstituents and the identification of beneficial herbal combinations that act synergistically to provide therapeutic effects. They almost have an acceptable impact and are safe, which makes them one of the top-choice, carefully chosen medications. Additionally, the Ayurvedic herbal compositions preferred oral administration methods.

Drugs in liquid form have some limitations, yet there is a great deal of public demand and expectation for these formulations. Furthermore, some formulations work better as liquids and are frequently utilized by adults or young children who have trouble in swallowing solid oral dosage forms. Most herbal supplements taken orally fall under the category of liquid dosage forms, either single or combined with other drugs. Designing and manufacturing herbal oral liquid formulation remains a challenge in contemporary pharmaceuticals [3].

2.Material and Methods

2.1 Collection and Authentication of Plant Material

The selected plant materials required for the present investigation such as RCL, MOL, AIL, TCLS, CCL were obtained from the different areas of Latur and Osmanabad

district, Maharashtra, India. Special precaution was taken to gather only healthy plant materials and to keep out foreign

materials. Plant herbarium sheets were produced and submitted to Department of Botany, Botanical survey of India for its authentication. Further the plants were identified and authenticated by renowned botanist Prof. D. L. Shirodkar from Department of Botany, Botanical Survey of India having authentication voucher number BSI/WRC/Iden.Cer./2021/3108210000452. After collection These plant samples were authenticated and thoroughly cleaned using distilled and running tap water before being allowed to air dry for a period at room temperature. Following that, the plant material was uncontaminatedly dried in the shade for three to four weeks. Dried plant material was crushed coarsely with an electric grinder. The powdered plant material was evaluated for color, flavor, texture, and taste. This dried plant material was stored for use in future studies in an airtight container.

2.2 Chemical reagents

Analytical grade chemicals and solvents were employed in this investigation.

2.3 Extraction

Using a Soxhlet apparatus, plant materials that had been dried in air and coarsely ground were first defatted with petroleum ether and then they were extracted successively using a series of solvents in increasing order of polarity, including chloroform, ethyl acetate and ethanol. A rotary flash evaporator operating at low pressure was used to concentrate the extracts, and the residue was then dried in a desiccator over sodium sulfite. After Following drying, corresponding extracts were weighed, the % yield was calculated, and they were then placed in airtight container [4,5, 6].

2.4 Formulation

A 100 ml of polyherbal Suspension was made by combining dried ethanolic extracts of RCL, MOL, AIL, TCLS, CCL (Table1).

2.4.1 Development of Polyherbal Suspension Dosage Form

A 100 ml suspension of ethanolic extracts from RCL, MOL, AIL, TCLS, CCL can be made by using the formula shown in Table 1. Using an appropriate suspending agent (Tween 80) and sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC) in a 1:1:1 [2, 3] ratio along with other excipients, the dried ethanolic extracts of selected plant materials were triturated in a mortar and pestle to

produce the polyherbal suspension. Water was used to triturate each of the materials listed above. Next, while continuously triturating the aforesaid aqueous medium in a mortar and pestle, the preservative and flavoring ingredient (lemon oil) was added. PHF-A, PHF-B, and PHF-C are three possible suspension formulations that were made using 1%, 1.5%, and 2% aqueous sodium CMC solution, respectively. To obtain uniform product, purified water was added at the end and make up the volume up to 100 ml through continuous trituration (Table 2). All polyherbal formulations made from extracts of RCL, MOL, AIL, TCLS, CCL (Fig. 1) were further evaluated in accordance with standards.

2.4.2 *Phytochemical Screening of the polyherbal formulation* [7].

The existence of proteins, carbohydrates, alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and other substances was discovered by the phytochemical screening of the polyherbal formulation (Table 3).

2.4.5 *Evaluation Parameters of the Polyherbal Suspension* [8, 9, 10, 11].

All three polyherbal formulations were assessed for number of characteristics such as aesthetic characteristics, pH, viscosity, sedimentation volume, re-dispersibility, zeta potential, crystal growth etc.

2.4.5.1 *Organoleptic Properties/Aesthetic Characteristics*

The following criteria, such as color, flavor, taste and texture were used to assess the organoleptic characteristics of the Polyherbal Suspension (Table 4).

2.4.5.2 *Accelerated stability studies*

For polyherbal formulations containing bioactive ingredients, accelerated stability experiments were carried out by incubating the samples for three months at 8°C, room temperature, and 45°C±2 with 75%±5% humidity. The various parameters such as sedimentation volume, viscosity, re-dispersibility, pH, zeta potential, Crystal growth was observed for optimized formulation at time intervals of 1-3 months.

a. Sedimentation volume:

The ratio of the final sediment height to the initial suspension height when the suspension settles in a cylinder under suitable standard circumstances is known as the sedimentation volume. A measured volume of suspension was kept in an undisturbed state in a graduated cylinder for a predetermined amount of time in order to evaluate it. It should be noted that the volume of the sediment is indicated as the ultimate height.

$$F=Hu / Ho$$

b. Redispersibility

A measurement cycle was used to allow the suspension to settle. After closing the cylinder's mouth and inverting it 180 degrees, A calculation was made to determine how many inversions would be needed to bring about a uniform suspension.

c. Rheology

Using the following formula, it was determined how long it would take for each suspension sample to go through a 10 ml pipette.

Flow rate = Volume of Pipette (ml) / Flow rates of (seconds)

d. pH

The pH meter (Eutech) was used to determine pH of polyherbal.

e. Determination of viscosity

A Brookfield viscometer type III with spindle 2 running at 250 rpm was used to measure the viscosity of polyherbal solutions. The results of all computations were acquired as mean values, and each calculation was done three times.

f. Particles size analysis:

One crucial component of suspension stability is the distribution of particle sizes within it. Optical microscopy was used to measure the particle size distribution in diluted samples.

g. Crystal growth

Crystal development, which typically happens because of changes in temperature during storage and creating smaller dimensions, might further impair the stability of polyherbal suspensions. The crystal formulations at room temperature 8°C and 45°C were determined.

h. Zeta Potential Determination

To understand the behavior of a dispersive system, the Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) method and the Malvern Zeta sizer Nano-ZS series automated inspection system at 25 ± 0.5 were used to analyze the zeta potential of suspension. (Fig. 2)

3. Result and Discussion

Polyherbal suspensions were produced as per (Table 1 and Table 2) shown in Fig.1 as follows;

Fig. 1 Photographs of Polyherbal Formulations

Above formulated polyherbal suspensions were further analyzed for different parameters as follow such as;

3.1 Organoleptic properties of polyherbal suspension

It was noted that the three formulation PHF-A, PHF-B and PHF-C have similar morphological characteristics such as greenish black in colour, slight bitter taste with a characteristic odour and liquid in nature, (Table 3).

3.2 Physicochemical properties of polyherbal suspension

Polyherbal suspensions were produced and examined for different parameters as follows, such as sedimentation volume, redispersibility, pH, viscosity, flow rate, zeta potential, crystal growth and phytochemical investigation.

Phytochemical screening of polyherbal formulations showed the presence of phytoconstituents such as phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, glycosides and terpenoids whereas Saponin was absent in the formulation as mentioned in (Table 4). In PHF-A, it was noted that the density ranged from (1.032), the sedimentation volume ranged from (0.98), the pH ranged from (4.46), the viscosity was (13.87), zeta potential (-24.0) and the quick flow rate was (18 seconds) per 5 ml of formulation (Table 5). As compared to PHF-A, it was found that the sedimentation

volume in PHF-B ranged from (0.98). This was attributed to an increase in the concentration of Sodium CMC, which also had an impact on the viscosity (26.09 cP), pH (5.09), decrease in formulation flow rate (39 seconds) per 5 ml of formulation, particle size was around (12.85 μm), zeta potential (-19.0) and density ranging from (1.037) (Table 5).

PHF-C has a greenish-black color, a slightly bitter taste and characteristic odour when it is at room temperature (RT) between 8° and 45°C. At varying temperatures, this suspension maintained its pleasant appearance and texture without changing. The suspension's pH, which is 5.80 after storage, indicates that there have been no noticeable alterations. The viscosity of the PHF-C suspension was found to be adequate, with a coefficient of 101.22 cP, zeta potential was -14.0 and a flow rate of 65 seconds per 5 ml indicating satisfactory rheological behavior. Since the sedimentation volume is close to the permitted limit of 1, as time went on, there were no noticeable changes in it. (Table 5).

The PHF-C formulation that had been optimized was sealed and put within a stability test chamber and subjected to stability studies under accelerated storage condition for 3 months in accordance to International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines at room temperature (RT) 8°C and 45°C. The suspension was analyzed for checking pH, Viscosity, crystal growth, redispersibility, zeta potential and change in particle size at the interval of 0-3 month's studies. Every result was evaluated against the final formulation shown in (Table 6). The PHF-C oral suspension formulation's characteristics during the stability period were a minor increase in particle size, but even so, it was still well within the acceptable limit.

Fig. 2 Graph of Zeta Potential

Table 1: General Formula for the Development of Polyherbal Formulation

Sr. No.	Name of ingredient	Quantity
01	Bio-active extract	1-5 gm
02	Tween 80	0.1 %V/V
03	Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC)	2 %
04	Methyl paraben	0.20 %W/V
05	Lemon oil	0.01 %ml
06	Distilled /Purified water	Up to 100 ml

Table 2: Composition of Different Polyherbal Formulation Development

Sr. No.	Name of Ingredient	Polyherbal Formulation		
		PHF-A	PHF-B	PHF-C
01	Ethanollic extract of R.C.	0.5 g	0.5 g	0.5 g
02	Ethanollic extract of M.O.	0.5 g	0.5 g	0.5 g
03	Ethanollic extract of A.I.	0.5 g	0.5 g	0.5 g
04	Ethanollic extract of T.C.	0.5 g	0.5 g	0.5 g
05	Ethanollic extract of C.C.	0.5 g	0.5 g	0.5 g
06	Tween 80	0.3% v/v	0.2 %v/v	0.1 % v/v
07	Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC)	1 %	1.5 %	2 %
08	Methyl paraben	0.20 % w/v	0.20 %w/v	0.20 %w/v
09	Lemon oil	0.01 %v/v	0.01 % v/v	0.01 % v/v
10	Distilled /Purified water	Up to 100 ml	Up to 100 ml	Up to 100 ml

Table 3: Organoleptic Characters of The Polyherbal Formulation

Sr. No.	Parameter	PHF-A	PHF-B	PHF-C
01	Nature	Liquid Suspension	Liquid Suspension	Liquid Suspension
02	Colour	Greenish Black	Greenish Black	Greenish Black
03	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
04	Taste	Slightly Bitter	Slightly Bitter	Slightly Bitter

Table 4: Phytochemical Investigation of the Polyherbal Formulation

Sr. No.	Phytoconstituents	Polyherbal Formulation		
		PHF-A	PHF-B	PHF-C
01	Carbohydrate	+	+	+
02	Glycoside	+	+	+
03	Protein	+	+	+
04	Steroids	++	++	++
05	Terpenoids	+	+	+
06	Tannins	+	+	+
07	Saponin	-	-	-
08	Phenols	++	++	++
09	Alkaloids	+	+	+
10	Flavonoids	++	++	++

Table 5: Physicochemical Parameters of Formulated Polyherbal Suspensions

Formulation	Sedimentation volume	Redispersibility	Flow rate	pH	Particle size	Viscosity	Crystal Growth	Zeta Potential	Density
PHF- A	0.98	Poor	5 ml /18 sec	4.46	13.61 μm	13.87 cP	No	-24.0	1.032
PHF- B	0.98	Good	5 ml / 39 sec	5.09	12.85 μm	26.09 cP	No	-19.0	1.037
PHF- C	0.99	Excellent	5 ml /59 sec	5.80	12.90 μm	97.24 cP	No	-14.0	1.092

Table 6: Accelerated Stability Study of Optimized Polyherbal Formulation PHF-C at RT 8^oC, 45^oC.

Time in days	8 ^o C									45 ^o C								
	Sedimentation volume	Redispersibility	Flow rate	pH	Particle size	Viscosity	Crystal Growth	Zeta potential	Density	Sedimentation volume	Redispersibility	Flow rate	pH	Particle size	Viscosity	Crystal Growth	Zeta potential	Density
0	0.99	Excellent	5 ml /59 sec	5.80	12.90 μm	97.24 cP	No	-14.0	1.092	0.99	Excellent	5 ml /59 sec	5.80	12.90 μm	97.24 cP	No	-14.0	1.092
30	0.99	Excellent	5 ml /59 sec	5.80	12.90 μm	98.24 cP	No	-14.0	1.093	0.99	Excellent	5 ml /59 sec	5.80	12.90 μm	98.24 cP	No	-14.0	1.093
45	0.99	Excellent	5 ml /61 sec	5.80	12.93 μm	99.24 cP	No	-13.0	1.094	0.99	Excellent	5 ml /61 sec	5.80	12.93 μm	99.24 cP	No	-13.0	1.094
60	0.98	Excellent	5 ml /62 sec	5.80	12.93 μm	99.24 cP	No	-13.0	1.094	0.98	Excellent	5 ml /62 sec	5.80	12.93 μm	99.24 cP	No	-13.0	1.094
90	0.98	Excellent	5 ml /63 sec	5.80	12.98 μm	101.2 cP	No	-12.0	1.095	0.98	Excellent	5 ml /63 sec	5.80	12.98 μm	101.2 cP	No	-12.0	1.095

4. Conclusion

The current study shows that the polyherbal formulation contained bioactive substances such as flavonoids, polyphenols, terpenoids, steroids, alkaloids, and glycosides. Since liquid dosage forms can overcome swallowing difficulties; they are preferable over solid dosage forms in children and the elderly. The majorities of Ayurvedic formulations is created in liquid form and are typically combined with more than two crude drugs. Among different oral dosage forms, pharmaceutical suspension is one of the most dependable and well-liked formulations due to its simple swallowing and flexible administration. Using the trituration process and appropriate suspending agent together with other excipients, ethanolic extracts of chosen plants were used to create the polyherbal suspension. After doing research with different concentrations of Sodium CMC, significant changes were seen in sedimentation, viscosity, and other physicochemical characteristics. As per the observations the polyherbal formulation's organoleptic and physicochemical qualities did not change much, according to the results of PHF-C's accelerated stability experiments, and all stability parameters remain stable, acceptable, and optimal at different temperatures.

Results of the above polyherbal suspension indicated the presence of flavonoids and other important phytochemicals. So, this polyherbal formulation can be further processed for evaluation of their hepatoprotective activity in future.

5. Future Prospects

Presently we worked on development and standardization of polyherbal suspension but in future we planned for In-vivo Hepatoprotective study for this polyherbal suspension.

6. Conflict Of Interest

No conflict of interest.

7. Abbreviations

PHF – Polyherbal Formulation

RT - Room Temperature

CMC - Carboxy Methyl Cellulose

cP – Centipoises

RC - *Ricinus communis*

MO - *Moringa oleifera*

AI - *Azadirachta indica*

TC - *Tinospora cordifolia*

CC - *Cymbopogon citrates*

L - Leaves,

LS - Leaves & Stem

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References

1. R.B. Sharma and R. Verma, "Development of hepatoprotective polyherbal formulation from methanolic extracts of stems of *Berberis aristata*, fruits of *Piper longum* and roots of *Boerhaavia diffusa*." The Pharma Innovation Journal; vol.9(3), pp.21-25,2020.
2. P.M. Dandagi, M.B. Patil, V.S. Mastiholimath, "Development and Evaluation of A Hepatoprotective Polyherbal Formulation Containing Some Indigenous Medicinal Plants," Ind J Pharm Sci; vol.70(2), pp. 265-8, 2008.
3. S.M. Mahajan, D.T. Baviskar, "Formulation Development and Evaluation of Polyherbal Suspension of Some Medicinal Plants," Int J Cur Res Rev; vol.13(12), pp.100,2021.
4. C.K. Kokate, Practical Pharmacognosy, 17th edition; Nirali Prakashan, 1999:7-9, 115-21, 123-5.
5. V.D. Rangari. Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, 1st edition; Career Publications, 2002: 356-60.
6. Remington; Vol-I. The Science and Practice of Pharmacy, 19th edition; Easton: Mack Publishing Company, 1995:551-3.
7. K.R. Khandelwal, Practical Pharmacognosy, 19th edition; Nirali prakashan, 2008:11-4, 146-57.

8. M.Y. Gaikwad, D.S. Thorat, "Formulation and Characterization of Herbal Antidiabetic Suspension," *Inter. J. Pharmao2*; vol.4(3), pp. 2582-4708,070-073, 2022.
9. R. S. Shivarkar, S. B. Bhise, V. RM. Gupta, N. S. Kulkarni et al, "Formulation Development and Evaluation of a Polyherbal Suspension Containing *Curcuma longa*, *Ocimum sanctum* and *Azadirachta indica* With Improved Antimicrobial Activity," *Journal of natural remedies*; vol.23 (3), pp.2320-3358, 2023.
10. D. Kumar, A. Dharmendra, "Formulation and Evaluation of a Polyherbal Suspension of *Aloe barbadensis* (Eeab), *Salix tetrasperma* (Eest) and *Tenacetum parthenium* (Eetp), *Jptcp*; vol.29(04) pp.1525-1530, 2022.
11. S. Jain, A. Khan, H. Anwane, et al, "Formulation, Development and Evaluation of polyherbal formulation for Antispasmodic Activity," *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*; vol.13(10) pp.3552-3558, 2022.